

A Preliminary Observation of Parasite Infestation on Blood Cockles (*Anadara granosa*) and Tropical Oyster (*Crassostrea iredalei*) in Northern Peninsular Malaysia

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Abstract: The blood cockle (*Anadara granosa*) and the tropical oyster (*Crassostrea iredalei*) are the two main molluscan species cultured in Malaysia, contributing 92.4% of the total mollusc production for the years 1997-2000. As no report or specific study on the molluscan disease problem in Malaysia was available, the study was conducted to determine the status of the parasitic infestation in these two species under culture conditions. Gross observation and histological examinations showed no significant pathogens except some light infestation by spores (gregarines) and trematodes. The presence of digenea in the digestive gland of blood cockles may be indicative of their role as intermediate hosts for the marine digenea. However, the role of blood cockle serving as an immediate host to marine trematodes has yet to be determined.

Abstrak: Kerang darah (*Anadara granosa*) dan tiram tropika (*Crassostrea iredalei*) merupakan dua spesies utama dalam ternakan moluska di Malaysia. Kedua-dua spesies ini menyumbang 92.4% daripada jumlah keseluruhan pengeluaran moluska dalam tempoh 1997-2000. Memandangkan tiada laporan atau kajian yang spesifik mengenai kajian penyakit moluska di Malaysia, kajian ini telah dijalankan untuk mendapatkan status infestasi parasit dalam dua spesies ternakan moluska utama di Malaysia. Pemerhatian kasar dan pemeriksaan histologi menunjukkan tiada patogen yang signifikan kecuali beberapa infestasi ringan oleh spora gregarina dan trematoda. Kehadiran digenea dalam kelenjar penghadaman kerang mungkin menunjukkan peranan mereka sebagai perumah sementara terhadap digenea marin. Walau bagaimanapun, peranan kerang sebagai perumah sementara terhadap trematoda marin masih belum ditentukan.

Keywords: Parasite, histology, blood cockles, tropical oyster

In Malaysia, the main bulk of the aquaculture production comes from molluscs such as the blood cockle (*Anadara granosa*), oysters (*Crassostrea iredalei*, *C. belcheri* and *Saccostrea cucullata*) and the mussel (*Perna viridis*). In year 2000, the mollusc production was dominated by cockles (38%) and only 7% by mussels and oysters (Anon., 2000). The blood cockle and tropical oyster (*C. iredalei*) contributed 92.4% of the total production of molluscs for the years 1997-2000 (Anon., 1997; 1998; 1999; 2000). Both species are widely cultured and distributed in sheltered areas along the west coast of Kedah, Perak, Penang and Selangor, east coast of Kelantan and Terengganu and southern Johor.

Despite its commercial importance, there were no monitoring programs to study the mollusc diseases in Malaysia as both expertise and facilities are lacking compared to the other countries (Sindermann, 1990; Imanaka *et al.*, 2001; Itoh, 2002). However, in 1999 the Asia-Pacific Regional Program on Molluscan Health Management under Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and Network of Aquaculture Centres in the Asia-Pacific (NACA) recognized the need to establish baseline expertise that will provide the foundation for countries in the Asia Pacific region to develop their own national programs for molluscan assessment and monitoring, risk analyses and control of epizootics.

The program consists of three phases listed as follows:

Phase I: Training course on Basic Molluscan Health Management (1999)

Phase II: Training Workshop: Evaluation of Country-Specific Survey Results, Manual Preparation and Follow-up training of Level II/III Molluscan Disease Diagnosis (2002) and

Phase III: Tier II/III Follow-up Training, Evaluation of Support and Results (2003). The outputs presented here are based on the results from Phase I and II.

This survey provides some baseline information on parasitic infestation of important molluscan species particularly *C. iredalei* and *A. granosa* cultured in Malaysia via gross and histological observations (Photo 1). A total of 34 tropical oysters (mean shell length 80.93 mm and width 81.60 mm) and 33 blood cockles (mean shell length 37.60 mm and width 22.10 mm) were collected and examined for parasitic infestation from year 2000 till 2002. Gross observation on tropical oysters showed the presence of polydora (27/34), shell discolouration (25/34), biofouling (18/34), mantle retraction (7/34), gill discolouration (5/34), gill deformities (2/34), abnormal shape (1/34) and co-habitants (1/34) (Photo 2). As for the blood cockles, only cliona (2/33) and shell discolouration (3/33) were observed. Fouling organisms such as barnacles and polydora were found mostly on the shell surface of oysters. Small crabs (*Pinnotheres* sp) were also found on the soft-tissues of oysters. Results from histological observation showed that both species were found to be infected with gymnospires and oocysts of gregarines, *Nematopsis* spp. Gregarine spores were found in one or uninucleate vermiform sporozoites in gill and connective tissue of various organs (Photo 3). They were most prevalent in the gills. Tropical oysters had a prevalence of 0.5 with 0.52 in blood cockles. Infestations of immature stages of trematodes as sporocyst were found in the digestive gland of blood cockles (Photo 4). The whole tubule system of the digestive tissue of blood cockles was almost compressed by the large numbers of immature stages of sporocysts lodged in between the tubules. However, the prevalence of trematodes infestation was low (0.06).

Though the results showed that gymnospires of gregarines (*Nematopsis* sp.) occurred most frequently in many of the specimens from tropical oysters (19/34) and blood cockles (17/33), no significant negative effects on their health were noted. Bower & McGladdery (2001) reported that gymnospires and oocysts of gregarines were usually associated with a focal, benign inflammatory response without serious effect or damage on the host. Immature stages of digenean such as sporocysts and cercariae could occasionally be present (2/33 or 0.06% infection) in the digestive glands of the blood cockles. According to Ginetsinkaya (1988), the tubule system could be compressed and blocked as the immature parasites developed which might affect the function of the digestive system.

Photo 1: Species used in the study. A). Tropical oyster (*Crassostrea iredalei*) and B). Blood Cockle (*Anadara granosa*).

Photo 2: Gross observation on tropical oyster . A). Biofouling B). Polydora C). Gill discolouration and D).Co-habitants

Photo 3: Parasitism by gregarines, gymnosporidiosis (arrowed) infections in connective tissue (A) and gill (B) of tropical oyster. H & E. A & B: 10x. 1 cm = 9 μ m

Photo 4: Parasitism by trematodes, digenea infestations of sporocysts (A) and immature cercariae stage (B) in digestive gland of blood cockles. H&E, A: 10x, 1 cm = 479 μ m and B: 40x, 1 cm = 124 μ m

The present study provided the basic information on the prevalence of infestation of parasitism by gregarines and trematodes on the blood cockle and oysters in Northern Peninsular Malaysia. Infestation of digenea at the digestive gland of the blood cockle indicated that it can also serve as an intermediate hosts for the marine digenea. Hence, the present study has opened up a wide field for future investigation on the blood cockle as another candidate for the immediate host of marine trematodes in Malaysia.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank NACA for the travel grant to attend the Phase II: Training Workshop: Evaluation of Country-Specific Survey Results, Manual Preparation and Follow-up training of Level II/III Molluscan Disease Diagnosis (2002) in Brisbane, Australia. Thanks are also due to Mr. Chuah Toh Tyre for comments on the manuscript.

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